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Research Article

**AWARENESS TOWARD COMPLEMENTARY AND
SUBSTITUTE MEDICINE AMONGST MEDICAL STUDENTS**¹Dr. Kinza Asghar, ¹Dr. Kamran Awais Islam, ²Dr. Iqra Marjan¹Government Kot Khawaja Saeed Teaching Hospital, KEMU, Lahore²Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi**Abstract:**

Objectives: The aim of this research work is to decide about the level of acquaintance and behaviour of the medical students.

Methodology: This research was conducted in Mayo Hospital Lahore out in the month of April 2017. Four hundred and one medical students took part in this research work. The opinion poll consists the question about demography and multiple choice questions about the fourteen recently utilized alternative treatments. We asked five more things to evaluate the behaviours of the students towards the alternative medicines. This all information was gathered from the students for further analysis.

Results: The awareness about the medicines, the Chinese method of healing (Tai Chi), medicines knowledge necessary for living, massage, a Japanese method of alternative medicines (reiki), pray and treatment with the help of herbs were varying among female and male participants of this study. The most famous modality in all the students of medical was hypnosis. We concluded from this research that use of internet was actual foundation of this data about complementary and alternative medicine modalities for the both sex. More than sixty-four percent students were found with firm believe that there are many advantages of the complementary and alternative medicine modalities.

Conclusions: In this research work, the positive behaviour toward complementary and alternative medicine was discovered very high but it was much lower than the most of other research works carried out in different other countries of the world.

Keywords: Complementary, CAM, alternative medicine, reiki, chi, modality, demography.

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INTRODUCTION:

The important rise in the utilization of the alternative medicines is noticed in recent time in the whole world [1-4]. An ever increasing curiosity in the introduction and combination of complementary and alternative medicine into the syllabus of the medical students was not found in USA only but in all countries of the world, with the rise in the use of complementary and alternative medicine [5-8]. There are a lot of various research works carried out in various countries of the world to confirm the awareness and behaviour students of nursing and medical schools, and staff of the hospital about complementary and alternative medicine [8-17]. In most of the research works, awareness, positive inclination and behaviour of the participants was discovered very high, the outcomes of those research works were different according to sex, class or the schools in which students were getting knowledge [5, 10-16]. The objective of this research work was conclude the awareness level of the students and to evaluate the disparity of level of awareness and optimistic attitude with respect to gender or class of the medical students.

METHODOLOGY:

The research was carried out in the month of April 2017. The participation rate was more than sixty-two percent. Four hundred and one students were selected for this research work. The opinion poll method was used which consist the questions of demography without the identification of the participant name and questions having options regarding the fourteen recently utilization complementary and alternative

medicine during treatments. We interrogated 5 more questions to evaluate the behaviour of participants towards complementary and alternative medicine which was out from the medical students of America [18]. The opinion poll was carried out in the first three classes of their course and last three classes in the practical working areas.

Two interrogators were prepared to reaction the questions asked by first 3 classes because of their hectic medical activities, the attendance of the last 3 classes in the practical rooms was not up to the mark. We did not tell anything regarding complementary and alternative medicine to the participants before or after the completion of this questionnaire. The SPSS software version eleven was used for the analysis and also Chi square test applied. The statistically significant was acknowledged with a P value of $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

Three hundred and seventy-four were the male participants and only twenty-seven were the female participants. The largest group was the medical students of third year class and participants from sixth class formed the smallest group as described in Table-1. The awareness about the medicines, Chinese method of treatment, massage, Japanese method of alternation of medicines, prays and treatments by herbs were found different among females and male's participants. The female's participants were more aware about the Chinese and Japanese methods of alteration of medicines but the male participants were more aware about the massage, medicines, prays and treatments by herbs.

Table-I: Characteristics of students	
Characteristics	Total= 401, n (%)
Gender	
Male	374 (93.3)
Female	27 (6.7)
Medical class	
1	73 (18.1)
2	56 (14.0)
3	91 (22.7)
4	68 (17.0)
5	72 (18.0)
6	41 (10.2)

Hypnosis was the most frequent modality in the male participants of the research work and acupuncture was most common in the female participants of this study work as described in Table-2.

We found an important disparity about the awareness of three modalities of complementary and alternative medicine between different medical classes. The students of third year class were found good knowledge of osteopathy & spirituality but the students of the fifth year class were found with best knowledge for feedback. The most recognized modality among students of all the classes was

hypnosis. Medicines made up of herbs, meditation, acupuncture, prayers and massage were known by the half of the participants taking part in this research work as described in Table-3. We concluded in this research work that the awareness about the alternative medicines was much in use by the female participants than the male ones. The most well-known source of information about CAM among the participants was internet. More than ninety-two percent females and more than eighty-seven percent females were getting help from internet. The participants were also getting help from books, newspapers, journals, TV and radio.

Table-II: The knowledge of students about CAM modalities according to gender

CAM modalities	(n=27)(%)	(n= 374)(%)
Biofeedback	37	30.7
Hypnosis	77.8	89.8
Meditation	66.7	84.8
Tai Chi #	40.7	28.1
Acupuncture	81.5	81.8
Ayuverdic medicine #	33.3	17.1
Chiropractic	14.8	12.8
Massage #	55.6	60.7
Osteopathy	14.8	27.8
Reiki#	48.1	23
Spirituality #	51.9	69
Herbal medicine #	40.7	73.3
Homeopathy	22.2	16.6
Nutritional Support #	40.7	58.3

The percentage of the participants who were in favour of the advantages of the modalities of complementary and alternative medicine was found about sixty-five percent. Female participants were more inclined towards the use of complementary and alternative medicine than the male participants of the study but there were found no disparity in statistically significant.

CAM modality	Medical class						P value*
	1st%	2nd%	3rd%	4th%	5th%	6th%	
Biofeedback	20.5	19.6	20.9	36.8	55.6	36.6	<0.001
Hypnosis	91.8	94.6	91.2	88.2	86.1	78	>0.05
Meditation	86.3	85.7	81.3	86.8	81.9	78	>0.05
Tai Chi#	26	26.8	30.8	29.4	29.2	31.7	>0.05
Acupuncture	79.5	83.9	84.6	89.7	79.2	68.3	>0.05
Ayuverdic medicine#	20.5	14.3	11	17.6	23.6	26.8	>0.05
Chiropractic	16.8	10.7	4.4	16.2	15.3	19.5	>0.05
Massage#	57.5	69.6	68.1	60.3	50	53.7	>0.05
Osteopathy	17.8	25	45.1	27.9	18.1	19.5	<0.001
Reiki#	19.2	30.4	24.2	23.5	30.6	19.5	>0.05
Spirituality#	68.5	75	76.9	61.8	58.3	63.4	0.011
Herbal medicine#	75.3	66.1	69.2	77.9	72.2	61	>0.05
Homeopathy	11	21.4	18.7	13.2	25	9.8	>0.05
Nutritional support#	57.5	67.9	68.1	45.6	47.2	19.5	>0.05

We assessed the behaviour towards the complementary and alternative medicine by the utilization of five questions and we were able to find some differences in the statistically significant between various classes of medical students. The medical classes of third year students were found more attractive towards the complementary and alternative medicine with positive approaches towards. The students of medical classes of fifth year were found with most negative approach toward complementary and alternative medicine as described in Table-4.

Table-IV: Medical students' attitudes towards complementary therapies

Item	Medical class						p value #
	1st%	2nd%	3rd%	4th%	5th%	6th%	
Complementary therapies are a threat to public health							
Strongly agree and agree	6.8	3.6	8.8	8.8	26.4	14.6	0.001
Neutral	31.5	42.9	36.3	33.8	29.2	22	
Strongly disagree and disagree	61.7	53.5	54.9	57.3	44.4	63.4	
Treatments not tested in a scientifically recognized manner should be discouraged.							
Strongly agree and agree	37	33.9	40.6	45.5	58.4	48.8	0.087
Neutral	30.2	35.7	29.7	35.3	20.8	26.8	
Strongly disagree and disagree	32.8	30.4	29.7	19.2	20.8	24.4	
Effects of complementary therapies are usually the result of a placebo effect							
Strongly agree and agree	15.1	28.6	22	25	48.6	39	
Neutral	69.8	50	51.6	44.1	29.2	29.3	<0.001
Strongly disagree and disagree	15.1	21.4	26.4	30.9	22.2	31.7	
Complementary therapies include ideas and methods from which conventional medicine could benefit							
Strongly agree and agree	58.8	67.8	70.3	58.8	68.1	68.3	
Neutral	28.2	28.6	22	29.4	19.4	14.6	0.267
Strongly disagree and disagree	12.4	3.6	7.7	11.8	12.5	17.1	
Most complementary therapies stimulate the body's natural therapeutic powers							
Strongly agree and agree	49.3	66	46.1	36.8	29.1	55.1	
Neutral	37	30.4	42.9	42.6	37.6	24.4	<0.001
Strongly disagree and disagree	13.7	3.6	11	20.6	33.3	19.5	

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